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CASE: TELEPRESENCE ROBOT – VIRTUAL, BUT ACTIVELY PRESENT TEACHER IN A PROTOTYPE LABORATORY

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, globalization is actively present in higher education. It includes global mobility of both people and knowledge. Research groups are international, and the mobility of students and teachers is continuously increasing. Technology enables us to interact over distances. This is good for the development of science and humanity. Impending climate change forces us to seriously think about the climate impact of air

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travel, for example. Meetings and lectures can quite easily be arranged virtually, but work done in laboratories usually requires an on-site teacher.

In this paper we present a case of building and testing a telepresence robot at the protolaboratory J. Hyneman Center at LUT university, Finland. There are several commercial telepresence robot manufacturers, and devices are produced for various needs, e.g. working in hazardous environments. We are building a relatively simple telepresence robot that can act as a substitute or a kind of an avatar for a physically distant teacher in a prototype laboratory. This device is built as a student project by using common and inexpensive components.

The aim of the paper is 1) to present briefly the building process of the device and 2) to present the first user experiences of the device in a prototype laboratory environment, from the standpoint of the both students and teachers. We also discuss the pros and cons of this kind of telepresence-related co-creation in engineering education. By doing so, we prove that the era of telepresence teaching in laboratories has already begun.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, higher education in universities is a global activity for which the free movement of both people and especially knowledge is important. Research groups are international and likewise, in education it is becoming more common for students to go on international exchanges as well as for researchers and teachers to work for periods of different lengths abroad [1]. However, short commutes, especially by air, put a strain on the climate and also incur costs, which in some cases can limit the flow of people and thus, information and knowledge. There are also other limitations that may prevent, for example, visiting lecturers and teachers to travel, like in 2020, when a pandemic stopped passenger traffic quite efficiently from around the world [2]. However, work in universities did not stop since technology enables us to interact over distances and continue research, teaching and learning. Meetings, lectures and many courses can easily be arranged in a virtual form. Laboratory work which is essential in many technical disciplines [3], is, however, more difficult to organize without an on-site teacher or instructor, and while verbal communication can relay content or instruction, the lack of a mobile physical presence of the instructor by only presenting a video image of them on a screen potentially limits the impact of the interaction with a student. Simple video conference calls have been common for a number of years but are generally accepted as inferior to in person meetings. Our proposition is that it would be preferable to enhance such interactions with a telepresence robot which has been engineered to replicate as much as is practical a person to person interaction.

Traditionally, university education has relied on lectures and training tasks that support them. In addition, there is often laboratory teaching in the technical disciplines. Often students work in laboratory on their own, but with the assistance of a teacher. In basic courses, laboratory work is usually planned in advance and it is up to the students to complete them in accordance with the instructions and data provided. Advanced courses give students more responsibility and can plan their laboratory work more on their own. In prototype laboratories, students work mostly

independently, but sometimes advice and comments from the teacher are still needed, especially when facing ill-defined and/or open-ended problems. This requires the presence of a teacher in the laboratory.

Sometimes the best expert can be far away from the university campus, even on another continent. Today, it is not always necessary to travel: virtual lectures and remote connections are already common and the COVID-19 epidemic boosted their use even more. In laboratory conditions, however, the mere presence on the computer screen may not be sufficient. In order to teach and guide effectively, the teacher should be able to move around the laboratory. In this case, the telepresence robot [4] can be of great help if it has enough human like functionality that the student starts to interact with it as they would with a person.

The telepresence robot does not function like some programmed robots which would require at least some artificial intelligence, i.e. the aim is not to help at some routine tasks, such as safety and lab instructions, answering the same type of questions over and over, monitoring students at work etc. Actually, it is a camera eye and robot arm connected to microphone, loudspeaker and moveable platform – all controlled remotely. The tool that wakes up to work only when someone remotely connects to it and starts using it. Several visiting teachers can use the same tool, and naturally, the knowledge of a robot thus depends a lot on the skills of the person using it. Naturally, students can ask questions via a robot to the person accompanying them, and when the person is elsewhere, the questions must also be asked in other ways, such as by e-mail.

Therefore, the discussion about pros and cons of the telepresence robot could be similar like discussion about some virtual meeting tool; what things we want to do with the tool, how they could be implemented technically, and what kind of guidelines are needed for both the teacher and the students to use it. An important consideration is also the potential misuse of the tool; are there unethical ways to use telepresence robots in an educational setting and how could they be prevented? When telepresence devices become more common, general rules for their use are also needed.

A group of students started building this kind of a telepresence robot, an avatar for a visiting teacher, in the protolab. This concept paper outlines how a robotics project can be introduced to help students understand all aspects of design, implementation and operation.

2. METHODOLOGY

The telepresence robot project was built by student teams as an exercise for “Processing of Analog Signals”, “Electronics Project Work”, “System Engineering Project Work” and “Technical Design” courses of mechanical engineering and electrical engineering departments. In this case, the staff of the protolab acts as the robot’s supervisor and defines the necessary functions, as well as monitors the progress of the work together with the course teachers. Since the telepresence robot project is experimental, it will have continuous development and hands-on testing, and the project will be ongoing even as student groups will change. It will be

motivating for student teams to build on top of each other's work on building and testing the robot.

The project will teach students - and teachers, too - to collaborate between different disciplines, and will provide hands-on experience of project work with meetings, testing, and different perspectives, all of which must be considered to build a working telepresence robot. It also teaches how to clarify work-related issues from previous factors, similar to documenting and guiding groups of students who will continue to work after the previous builders.

Another telepresence robot was built at the same time in M5 industries, San Francisco, and in this way, the university students were able to exchange experiences and thoughts with M5 industries group, and for example, try and learn what it's like to control a robot on another continent.

2.1. Definitions (what a robot should be able to do)

The idea was that a student team would build the first version of the telepresence device to be very modular and flexible, and do it with a relatively small budget. This was to prove that the concept works, and the plan would be to create a successive version of the device based on the learning experiences from the first one. The requirements for a telepresence robot were defined for the student team from the perspective of a client. In this case, the main consideration for re-examining the requirements to create a functioning robot was left to the student team.

The main operating environment of the device will be a proto workshop, so the area will be about 330m², consisting mainly of worktables and some manufacturing equipment in the larger space, and smaller workshops behind closed doors. The operating environment of the device effects the requirements and it needs to be able to move outside its main operating environment as well, although it will need to maintain an internet connection in order to be remote controlled.

2.1.1 Robot arm

The user of the telepresence device should be able to communicate and operate in a proto-workshop environment. A requirement is that the device should be able to see what is happening on the working tables, look at something on the floor, or face someone eye to eye. In addition to seeing, the telepresence device must be able to point things out and grasp objects, and all robot movements and functions must be remotely controllable.

2.1.2 Audiovisual

The most important feature the robot should have is that the operator of the device should have good, clear camera image in order to distinguish details from the prototypes and work which it will guide. If bandwidth is limited, devices might transmit data from only one camera, at the cost of lacking the depth perception achievable from stereo vision, or software could be designed to minimize bandwidth requirements but assigning areas like faces or center of frame to have higher definition, or not refreshing areas that are not changing.

The user of the telepresence device must hear the sounds around the device as if he were physically present, so multiple microphones might be needed. The user must be able to communicate by voice transmission, and the sound quality should be sufficient to make the speech very clear.

2.1.3 Movement

The telepresence robot must be able to go through normal doors, about 90 cm wide. It would also need to be able to go down typical aisles in a classroom or lab. University facilities are often maze-like and have many doors. However, the robot would not need to be able to open the doors itself if there is a human assistant made available to accompany it. Opening the door will be excluded from the initial requirements as it is considered a demanding operation and it would complicate the construction of the first robot too much. The robot should also fit in the elevators together with a guardian though, and it would not be too much to expect it to be able to push buttons or switches, such that if the facility is equipped with automatic doors it could move through them and operate elevators.

2.1.4 Basics and safety

The device must be rechargeable. The remote user does not need to be able to do this in the first iteration of the robot, as it is enough that a physically present guardian is able to do this without special training. The battery should last for at least about two hours of normal operation. The telepresence device must independently prevent collisions with, for example, pedestrians, glass doors and the like. A more comprehensive security arrangement was not included in this version as it is used under controlled conditions in the presence of persons. Successive iterations might benefit from 360 degree cameras or special purpose cameras that are able to clearly spot any potential collisions, not to mention using geo fencing to inhibit remote operators from making the robot go places it is not wanted.

2.2. Robot design and construction

The robotic system includes several components as shown in Fig. 1: a camera, a main processor for video processing and wireless communication, speakers for remote user audio, an embedded auxiliary processor (traction motor control), a manipulator arm, and batteries and required peripherals such as indicator lights. The following sections introduce these different aspects of the project [5].

Fig. 1. Simplified block chart of the telepresence robot system [5].

2.2.1. Robot arm

The BCN3D MOVEO was chosen as the robot hand. The most important requirements of the hand are the dimension of about a meter and the possibility to lift an object weighing a kilogram. Transmitting the robot arm position to a remote user via a 2D camera is not easy, due to the six controllable axes, therefore controlling the hand intuitively will be challenging.

It is possible to simulate the trajectories of the hand in advance and it would be possible to transfer these simulated trajectories to the hand via Arduino. However, this was not seen as important for the use of the robot and for this reason no digital position sensor was selected for the motors. However, the drive motors as well as their power supply and control electronics are oversized so that the component selections also work with a heavier robotic frame and it is possible to run all the motors simultaneously. The limit switches take care of the hand movement limits so that the hand does not damage itself by hitting the robot body or other parts of the hand. The user must make sure that the hand does not damage itself due to the environment.

2.2.2. Audiovisual

The function of audio playback in the robot is to enable two-way communication between the remote user and people in the vicinity of the robot. Thus, the robot needs both speakers and a microphone. Communication takes place using the main processor via the Internet. To amplify the audio signal, an audio amplifier circuit was built for the speakers.

Two Visaton DX 10-4 speaker elements were selected as speakers. The impedance of the speakers is 4 Ω and the rated power is 50 W. According to the sound requirements of the robot, the sound pressure must be at least 70 dB measured from

a distance of one meter. The required volume control option is currently available through the main processor operating system or network interface [5].

The camera chosen was Ricoh Theta V, due to high image quality and programmability through interfaces enable smooth streaming for the needs of the project. The camera has two wide-angle lenses on each side of the device.

Together, they cover a 360-degree field of view. The main features of the camera are 3840x1080 resolution video, which can be streamed to a computer via a USB cable.

The built-in microphone of the camera used in the robot has been found suitable for this use in preliminary tests, so a separate microphone is not required. The required microphone frequency range was defined in the specification as 85 - 10,000 Hz, this is likely to be the case, but it has not been verified by testing.

A 360-video viewing feature and virtual controllers for driving the robot and controlling the robot hand were implemented in the web interface. WebRTC technology is used for data transfer, which can achieve low latency [6]. The connection is between the two sides (P2P). Network interface and the signal server required connecting the two sides was placed in the Microsoft Azure cloud. The robot's main processor platform is Intel's NUC minicomputer. The computer transmits control commands via the serial bus to the microcontroller controlling the motors, as well as captures the image stream from the camera and forwards it. A screenshot of the user interface is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Robot web interface. The image of the 360-degree camera can be rotated with the mouse. Below the picture is a joystick that controls the robot's drive motor and swivel wheels. Each axis of the robot arm is controlled by a pair of buttons. [5]

2.2.3. Mechanics

A square aluminum profile was chosen as the robot body material. This was chosen in part because structure is easy to change if problems occur, secondly, the material is extremely easy to machine and join together. When the development of the robot continues, the body material will probably be changed to a less modular solution. The base of the robot body is assembled in Fig. 3. Rest of the parts are then stacked on top of the body of the frame. The base of the robot hand comes to a height of approx. 90 cm from the ground, so it can reach for the items on the table. Camera is attached on a pole as a highest point of the robot. This allows the camera to see anywhere around the robot. The base of the robot is about 50 cm wide, so the robot can pass through the doors.

The robot has swiveling front wheels that are steered by a stepper motor a bit like a normal car. This is a simple approach to implement in a prototype project. A differential was attached to the rear axle to improve the maneuverability of the robot. The steering angles of the front wheels were dimensioned in the prototype phase by utilizing the Ackermann condition.[5].

Fig. 3. Base of the robot

2.3. Testing

The testing of the prototype was scheduled for March, however SARS-CoV-2 pandemic caused delays in finalizing the design and testing of the student version of the telepresence device. Experience from other telepresence devices [7] [8] and the limited testing made it possible to inspect what the priorities should be when creating next version of the device.

The remote connection and use of a telepresence device was tested on May 26th. Students were allowed to test and use a telepresence device located at M5 Industries, San Francisco. This test session gave a sense of using the device and helped them design the device forward.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Learning experiences from the telepresence devices

One of the main issues that came up is the great degree of linkages between various aspects within this project. Building a telepresence robot is a very technological enterprise, but in the end, enabling people to act over a distance is paramount. On the technical side, a minimum level of functionality emerged. For example, it is imperative that latency should be as low as possible. There are numerous ways of optimizing it, by first identifying exactly where it occurs. It may not be from anything to do with the robot's processors. The bottleneck could quite easily be the internet because of bandwidth limitations or distance, or it could be the quantity of data that is being retrieved.

Coordinating behavior in a remote-controlled device is likely to be most compromised if camera resolution and latency are not adequate. Otherwise while many possible features are optional to have on a telepresence robot, in general it is best wherever possible as a default to at least replicate what a human would experience if they were there instead of the robot.

Along with transmitting high definition images, zooming in or any other way of getting a detailed image is adequate – as long as it does not cause latency. It may be necessary to give high definition only to portions of a given image, like elements that are changing, or elements like a human face, which can be done with existing algorithms.

A discussion arose about the human-like features of the robot. What qualities must it have in order for conversation to work through it and for teaching to become possible? Since the telepresence robot's primary function is to be a surrogate for interaction with humans, it should have something that is equivalent to a head or face, which would be able to acquire a face to face position. Ideally, it would also be able to move its head, with its camera and sensors, from a height of 1 meter (approximately desk top level) to a height of 2 meters in order to be at head height and line up face to face with an adult that is either seated or standing. Head movement should replicate that of a human as much as is practical, to make interaction with it similar to that between people. While it would be possible to have a simple pan and tilt movement of the surrogate head, like what a common camera gimbal has, having the head on a neck that can lean the head forward and up or down, side to side like a human's does could lend a more organic quality to the robot and broadcast the intent of the operator. Coordination of a head and neck turn with movement of the base for example can be choreographed through animation algorithms to happen sequentially; for example first the head and neck turns and then the base turns, which will provide a subtly more organic or life like presentation to people it is interacting with.

One is best served by not replicating literally everything a human does (like for example having an animated mechanical rubber human face), as much as capture the experience or intent. Not only is it complex and difficult to create a human face with the normal compliment of expressions but doing this commonly puts a robot in the well-known "uncanny valley" which is counterproductive. It would be preferable to

be done metaphorically, or with very similar functions that are more practical. For example, a screen with an image of a face on it is likely to be better than a rubber mechanical one; in general, if the robot is able to accomplish a task, it's not so important how. Secondly, there is no reason that improvements or additions to human functions cannot be had in such devices. Multispectral cameras can show a user more than what a human eye sees and amplified, or enhanced hearing could be provided. Things can be automatically recorded by the robot to be played back, or even physical feats like employing computer precision as a sort of augmentation to a movement- like drawing a perfectly straight line with a marker on paper that most people either can't do or do as well with hands alone is just one example. These things can be either just bonus features, or they could be seen to even the scales, considering that the robot will not be able to do normal things like sense touch and smell that are not practical to try to replicate, and that there are going to be intangible things an actual in person meeting will have that a telepresence robot would not be able to provide.

Having the base able to rotate in place and move in all directions smoothly will also enable it to fit and move in areas the same way a human would in close quarters. While the speed of the robot will be limited to normal human walking speed and would not be heavy or powerful enough to seriously injure a bystander, obviously the robot or things it runs into could be damaged if it hits them. It might be advisable to install a pleasant sound generator that comes on, so people present know when it is moving even if they are not watching it.

The above-mentioned large number of different connections forms the body of this project. There is a constant need of iterative reasoning and testing after every solution made. This came apparent both in the short and long term, that is within one semester and within an annual continuous and evolving project (this last in the form of challenges for the coming periods). Although we had an idea of this in advance, we still found that it would be good for students to have a stronger role as a tester, in addition to the role of builder. Technological development offers a lot of interesting things to do for creative minds, but the actual results will be seen only through learning. The project itself is one learning environment, but the real benefit of the device comes through other courses, teaching in laboratories.

These aspects highlight the need for a more structured process of testing during the next seasons: user experiences need to be collected, data analyzed, and utilized in subsequent design rounds. This outcome is clear, and expected, but it forms an interesting tension with the nature of this project. Because of the large number of different connections and iterative processes, it is not possible to proceed through a pre-planned linear project; or we would omit a large number of development steps because of the clarity of the process, and the sense of control. This sparked a debate: whether we teach rapid product development or manageable clear projects. It is likely that telepresence teaching in higher education organizations will increase in the future. Our aim was not to present a blueprint of ultra-modern telepresence device, but to illustrate that this technology can be produced as student projects. The telepresence technology enables visits by specialists in laboratories with less required time, costs and emissions compared to travel. It also opens the door to

actual improvements on the way we interact as a result of the ease of the act; people are under less stress if they are not jet lagged from travel or away from their families and the comforts of home, and we must keep in mind that even if we have effective medicines to deal with the current pandemic, the common cold flu and other illnesses – which have a comparably negative effect on people will be better avoided by having unnecessary contact outside one's local circle. However, this is just the beginning of a new era and, in addition to technical expertise, different pedagogies and ethical rules for action are needed. An important consideration is also the potential misuse of the tool; are there unethical ways to use telepresence robots in an educational setting and how could they be prevented? When telepresence devices become more common, general rules for their use are also needed. Future practical experiences with our telepresence robot in the prototype laboratory will help us to develop both technology and practice further. Perhaps in the coming years, a whole new culture will be created for teaching through telepresence robots. Between the potential advantages we have listed and the inevitable technological improvements in the human/machine interface that will come from the student crowd sourcing of changes we are encouraging students to make the designs, we may anticipate that this type of robot assisted remote teaching could become accepted as at least equivalent, if not superior at times to the standard method.

REFERENCES

- [1] Eurostat, (2019). Learning mobility statistics. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Learning_mobility_statistics, Referred 17.4.2020
- [2] Centers for disease control and prevention, (2020). COVID-19 Travel Recommendations by Country. Available at: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/travelers/map-and-travel-notices.html>, Referred 17.4.2020.
- [3] Feisel, L.D. and Rosa, A.J. (2005) 'The role of the laboratory in undergraduate engineering education', *Journal of Engineering Education*, 94(1), pp. 121–130. doi: 10.1002/j.2168-9830.2005.tb00833.x.
- [4] Kristoffersson, A., Coradeschi, S., & Loutfi, A. (2013). A review of mobile robotic telepresence. *Advances in Human - Computer Interaction*, 2013 doi:<http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.cc.lut.fi/10.1155/2013/902316>
- [5] Rahikainen H., Tuimala, L., Putkonen, A., Salminen, O., Grasbeck, K. (2020). *Telepresensirobotti – Loppuraportti*. System Engineering Project Work Analog signal processing Electronics Project Work course, final report. *(In Finnish)*
- [6] Jansen, B., Goodwin, T., Gupta, V., Kuipers, F. & Zussman, G. 2018. Performance Evaluation of WebRTC-based Video Conferencing. *ACM SIGMETRICS Performance Evaluation Review*, 45(3), pp. 56-68. doi:10.1145/3199524.319953

- [7] Edwards, A., Edwards, C., Pence, P. R., Harris, C. & Cambino, A. (2016). Robots in a classroom: Differences in students' credibility and learning between "teacher as robot" and "robot as teacher". Computers and human behavior. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.06.005>
- [8] Khojasteh, N. & Liu, C. (2019). Understanding Undergraduate Students' Experiences of Telepresence Robots on Campus, CSW'19, Poster presentation, November 9-13, Austin, TX, USA.